

Supplementary information

1. Illumination volume

Supplementary Figure 1 a, Experimental measurement of the illumination volume obtained by a tapered fiber inserted in the cortex of a fixed brain slice emitting light at 785 nm. The fiber outline is shown in white. The contour lines display the levels of relative intensity at 10 % (red), 20 % (green) and 50 % (cyan) of the maximum intensity. **b**, Numerical model of the illumination volume for a simulated TF inserted in a uniform scattering medium (see methods). As in panel a, the contour lines show the relative levels of intensity with respect to the maximum.

Supplementary Fig. 1 shows that the assumption of isotropic scattering allows a good prediction of the excitation profile in the region of tissue that receive most of excitation power density ($>50\%$ of the maximal intensity), which corresponds to a radius of about $150\ \mu\text{m}$ of tissue around the fiber. Moving farther from the fiber axis, the morphology of the brain appears to favor propagation perpendicular to the fiber axis relative to propagation along the fiber axis. We believe this is due to the presence of the corpus callosum, a largely myelinated structure that prevents light from traveling to deeper regions. We expect that this effect plays a limited role in our study because the bulk of the Raman signal arises from the vicinity of the fiber, as shown in the photometry maps, due to the progressive diminishment of both the excitation intensity and collection efficiency with the distance from the fiber. Nonetheless, we anticipate that future research, initiated for fluorescence fiber photometry in the visible range⁶⁰, might advance into deeper investigations also at near infrared wavelengths.

2. Optical systems and spectral validation

The bench-top system is based on two nested 4f optical paths that simultaneously conjugate the back facet of the TF with an excitation and a collection path (Supplementary Fig. 2a). In the excitation path, the back facet of the TF is conjugated with the output facet of a multimode fiber patch with the same core size. This optical system allows selectively outcoupling light across the whole optically active region of the taper, acting on the injection angle of the

excitation light to inject independent modal subsets (Supplementary Fig. 2b). The excitation light emerging from the patch cord is reflected by a dichroic mirror and is then relayed on the full core of the TF. In this way, we diminish the power density at the back of the TF for a given excitation power while disposing of the Raman background generated in the excitation fiber. At the same time, the collection path images the fiber back facet on the slits of the spectrometer and, consequently, on the spectrometer's camera. Although using mode-selective light injection to dynamically modulate the photometry regions is an intriguing perspective supported by this system (Supplementary Fig. 2b), this path is hindered by the limited number of modes that can be harnessed with NIR excitation using off-the-shelf multimode fibers with a manageable background (e.g. low-OH NA=0.22). The portable system, instead, was designed to be deployed in stereotaxic systems for *in vivo* recordings in neuroscience laboratories with limited space to host bulky optical components. As shown in Supplementary Fig. 2c, d, the optical scheme used in the benchtop case was compacted in a fiber-bench system, where the excitation emerging from a fiber-coupled laser was injected in the TF stub using two fiber-ports on perpendicular axes, optically connected through a dichroic mirror. The Raman signal collected by the TF was then injected in a detection fiber bundle, connected to a compact spectrometer, by a third fiber port on-axis with the TF stub. A laser line filter on the excitation line and a long pass filter in the detection arm were used to suppress the remaining excitation signal and the silica background.

To benchmark the two systems, we performed a validation in a phantom solution (olive oil) (Supplementary Fig. 2e). Then we compared the systems against conventional Raman spectra acquired in brain tissue without the fiber (Supplementary Fig. 2 f,g). We found that both systems can identify the relevant spectral features of conventional Raman spectra from brain tissue in the analyzed portion of the FP range (1300 cm^{-1} -1800 cm^{-1}) and in the HW range. In the FP range, the stronger Raman bands (e.g. 1440 cm^{-1} and 1660 cm^{-1}) can be identified on top of the fiber background in both systems. At the same time, the fiber background in the HW range is negligible in both setups. We note that the presence of the silica background does not impair the spectral resolution. However, the lower performances (resolution and sensitivity) of the compact portable spectrometer influence the recorded spectral features in the portable system. In particular, the strong bands of the FP range are less prominent above the silica signal and the bands in the HW range are less resolved than in the benchtop system. Nonetheless, the spectral features can be distinguished and analyzed, yielding robust results. As a reference we acquired the spectra from melanoma brain metastasis without the fiber (Supplementary Fig. 2h).

Supplementary Figure 2 a, Schematic of the benchtop optical system used in ex-vivo experiments. The optical paths of the nested 4f systems conjugating the tapered fiber (TF) back facet with the spectrometer slits and the excitation fiber are shown in different colors. Galvo: galvanometric mirror, MMF: multimode fiber, L1, L2: aspheric lenses, TF: tapered fiber, M: mirror, TL: Tube Lens, LPF: long pass filter, Spectro: spectrometer. **b**, selecting modal subset at the input of the TF results in spatially separated emission of excitation light along the taper cone. **c**, arrangement of the in vivo experiments using the portable system mounted on a stereotaxic rig. **d**, 3D schematic of the portable optical system used in in-vivo experiments. **e**, comparison of spectra of olive oil acquired using the benchtop system (green) and the portable system (red); for the portable system data, a background spectrum acquired with the TF in air was subtracted from the spectrum acquired in olive oil. **f**, examples of spectra acquired in the FP range (left) and in the HW range (right) using an objective lens on top of the brain surface

(top), using an implanted TF with the benchtop system in ex vivo brain (middle) and using an implanted TF with the portable system in vivo. Spectra are shown as average \pm standard deviation. **g**, Optical system without the fiber probe. **h**, Comparison of Raman spectra without the fiber measured on the tumor (magenta) and in the contralateral hemisphere (cyan) in both the FP and HW ranges. Spectra are shown as average \pm standard deviation in shaded color.

3. Principal Component Analysis

Spectra were assigned to clusters based on the spatial density in the projection plot of PC loadings (see Methods). Supplementary Fig. 3a shows an example of the decision plot. As shown in panel b, this approach allows for a robust classification of the spectra, based on histological labeling (see Methods) and spectral analysis of the PC loadings. Loadings extracted from ex vivo data from melanoma brain metastasis brains in the FP range (Supplementary Fig. 3c) show positive contribution from lipidic (1440 cm^{-1}) and amide I (1660 cm^{-1}) bands and silica background in PC2, while PC1 holds negative melanin peak (1400 cm^{-1}) and silica potentially showing an opposite contribution of tissue reflectivity (which in turn leads to variance within the silica signal) in the healthy vs cancer case. As shown in panel b, the the PC1 vs PC2 space shows good separation of the clusters discrimination. In the ex vivo HW range (Supplementary Fig. 3d). PC1 encodes a polynomial curve which we tentatively attributed to autofluorescence from melanin while PC2-PC3, instead reveal a different composition in terms of lipid/protein ratio. In the in vivo data, the loadings from the PCA before the CNN processing (Supplementary Figure 3e) show similar behaviors. PC1 and PC2 are consistent with the ex vivo case, with PC2 showing a positive contribution of silica background, lipidic band (1440 cm^{-1}) and amide I (1660 cm^{-1}) and a small yet present contribution from CH bands in the HW range. PC1 instead holds the combined features of negative fiber signal and melanin (1400 cm^{-1}) together with an autofluorescence carrier component extending in the HW. PC3 contains signals that are strongly influenced by occurrences of saturation in some of the measurements. After processing the data through the CNN (Supplementary Fig. 3f), PC2 appears to be closely correlated with melanin with strong bands centered at 980 cm^{-1} , 1400 cm^{-1} and an increase in the $1450\text{-}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band that might be linked to the combined effect of cellular proliferation, melanin (1590 cm^{-1}) and blood extravasation. PC1 has similar features yet it shows a strong negative contribution between $1500\text{-}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is difficult to attribute unambiguously. As discussed in the main text, the lower resolution of the portable system implies that the deep learning algorithm is less efficient in isolating the Raman signal from the silica background in this spectral region.

Supplementary Figure 3 a, Example of the decision plot based on cluster density: the outliers identify the centers of the putative clusters. **b**, Example 2D orthogonal projections of PCA points for the three most informative components for the ex vivo data in the fingerprint range **c**, PC loadings extracted from ex vivo data from melanoma brain metastasis brains in the fingerprint (FP) range. **d**, As in **c** for the high-wavenumber (HW) **e**, PC loadings extracted from in vivo data from melanoma brain metastasis. **f**, As in **e** for in vivo data after processing with the the convolutional neural network (CNN).

4. Validation of deep-learning suppression of the silica background

The network architecture is shown in Supplementary Fig. 5a. Starting from the raw spectra (Supplementary Fig. 5b), we obtained noisy and denoised Raman spectra with suppressed silica background (Supplementary Fig. 5c, d respectively). To validate the fidelity of the algorithm with respect to the native Raman signal, we compared the Raman signal acquired with the conventional system with the signal obtained from the fiber and processed via the CNN. In healthy regions, we found a remarkable agreement between the spectra taken in air and the ones taken with the fiber and processed with the CNN. Not only the main peaks had similar intensities and widths, but also the smaller spectral features could be extracted from the fiber signal. In cancer tissue, we observed that the CNN extracted the salient spectral features associated with the tumor such as the melanin peak at 1400 cm^{-1} , the suppression of lipidic bands at 1440 cm^{-1} and 1660 cm^{-1} , the melanin band at 1590 cm^{-1} and a peak at 1520 cm^{-1} tentatively attributed to cellular proliferation and blood serum components resulting from the rupturing of the blood brain barrier. We observed that the relative height and width of the peaks was not as closely associated with the benchmark spectrum as observed in the healthy regions. However, we believe this reflects native differences in the composition of the two measured

volumes. While the conventional system collects light from the surface of the brain, the fiber dives through the metastasis and interacts with a larger portion of tissue that has been invaded by cancer.

We then compared the spectra acquired through the benchtop system *ex vivo* before and after the CNN processing. Fig.2 a, c in the main text show the spectra before the CNN while Extended Data 5 g, h shows CNN processed spectra. We observed that the algorithm can successfully suppress the silica background to highlight the salient spectral features that characterize the presence of melanoma brain metastasis, such as: the presence of melanin bands at 1400 cm^{-1} and 1590 cm^{-1} , the suppression of lipid bands at 1440 cm^{-1} and the suppression of the amide I band at 1660 cm^{-1} . In the processed spectra, the broad band centered at 1600 cm^{-1} is suppressed and this highlights the 1590 cm^{-1} , that was previously combined with the background. At the same time, the CNN eliminates polynomial residues that might mask weaker bands, as the slope starting at 1725 cm^{-1} , which we have tentatively assigned to autofluorescence. It is interesting to consider that this autofluorescence appears to be stronger in the metastatic region and it offers, therefore, an opportunity for diagnostics that we have exploited with the ratiometric approach.

Supplementary Figure 4 *a*, Diagram of the network architecture, with cascaded levels to progressively isolate the Raman component from the raw-spectra. *b*, Raw Raman spectra acquired through the fiber with the benchtop system *c*, De-noised raman spectra after the full CNN processing. *d*, Comparison between the spectra acquired without the fiber and the spectra acquired through the fiber and processed with the CNN in healthy tissue. *e*, As in *d* for tissue invaded by cancer. *f*, CNN processed spectra acquired in *ex vivo* brain through the fiber; data from the spectra shown in Fig. 2a. *g*, As in *f* for the difference spectra shown in fig. 2c. Spectra are shown as average \pm standard deviation in shaded color.